

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

ORAL FILMS: RECENT APPROACHES

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 29/01/2021

Available online

01/03/2021

Keywords

Fast Dissolving Oral Film,
Alternative Route of
Administration,
Dosage Forms,
Pediatric and Geriatric
Patients.

ABSTRACT

Buccal drug delivery has become the most important route of administration of drug due to unwilling of oral administration of solid preparations by both pediatric and geriatric patients. This has led to development of alternate route of administration like film drug delivery system. Fast dissolving drug delivery systems were developed in 1970s as an alternative to syrups, capsules and tablets for pediatric and geriatric patients. They have been accepted easily as new drug delivery system because of easy administration, rapid drug absorption, better patient compliance and good bioavailability.

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Please cite this article in press as **B. Joshna et al.** Oral Films: Recent Approaches. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2021:11(02).

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INTRODUCTION

Among the routes of administration, oral route is the most acceptable route for patients. Many pharmaceutical companies have focused their research on developing alternative dosage form for pediatric and geriatric as well as nauseous patients. The recently developed approach is oral films, which help in increasing patient compliance by self-administration without swallowing and chewing. Generally, the disintegrating tablets are fragile and thus require special packing for storage and transport, but in the case of oral films, they are more reliable and easily handled.^[1]

Oral dissolving film or strip can be defined as “A dosage form which requires water dissolving polymer that hydrates the drug or the dosage form using saliva and adheres to the mucosa thereby disintegrates within few seconds, dissolves and releases the medication when placed on the tongue or oral cavity for oromucosal absorption.

ADVANTAGES

- Oral films have special advantages over other oral dosage forms given as follows:
- Dissolve rapidly and disintegrate in the oral cavity because of large surface area, which reduces dosage interval, improves onset of action, efficacy and safety profile of therapy.
- These are more flexible, compliant and are not brittle as ODT's (orally disintegrating tablets).
- They can be handled easily, transportation and storage.
- Accuracy in the administered dose from each strip or film.
- Pharmaceutical companies and customers practically accepted these films as an alternative of conventional OTC (over the counter) dosage forms such tablets etc. (Frey, 2006).^[2]
- Oral films are desirable for patient suffering from motion sickness, dysphagia and mental disorders.
- The drugs enter the systemic circulation, which reduces first pass metabolism.

DISADVANTAGES

- The main disadvantage is that large amount of drug or high dose cannot be incorporated into the film or strip. The dose should be between 1-30 mg.
- There are technical limitations for preparation of oral strips especially the thickness. Petri plates made up of glass cannot be used for casting.

CLASSIFICATION OF ORAL FILMS

There are three types of oral fast dissolving oral films:

1. Flash release films.
2. Mucoadhesive melt-away wafer.
3. Mucoadhesive sustained release wafers.

Flash release films

These are also known as oro films, which are very thin and small similar to a postal stamp containing API and other excipients. Due to their convenience and portability, they are widely accepted dosage forms for both pediatric as well as geriatric patients.

Mucoadhesive melt-away wafer

Mucoadhesive wafers are dosage forms, which contain a water-dissolving polymer, causing the film to adhere, hydrate and dissolve when placed on tongue or in the oral cavity. This allows the film to rapidly disintegrate and release the drug for intragastric and mucosal absorption.

Mucoadhesive sustained release wafer

These are multilayered structures composed of non-soluble polymers and poorly soluble excipients in which drug is dispersed in solution or suspension.

Table 1: Properties of oral films.

Properties	Flash release of water	Mucoadhesive Melt Away Water	Mucoadhesive Sustained Release Water
Area	2-8	2-7	2-4
Thickness	20-70	50-500	50-250
Structure	Single layer film	Multilayer system or single layer system	Multilayer system
Excipients	Soluble, highly hydrophilic polymers	Soluble, highly hydrophilic polymers	Low/ non-soluble polymers
Drug phase	Solid solution	Solid solution or suspended drug particle	Suspension or solid solution
Application	On the upper palate of the tongue	Gingival or Buccal region	Gingival (other region in the oral cavity)
Dissolution	Max 60 sec	Disintegration occurs in a few minutes, forming gel	Maximum 8-10 hrs
Site of action	Systemic or local	Systemic or local	Systemic or local

FORMULATION INGREDIENTS

1. Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient
2. Plasticizer
3. Strip forming polymer
4. Saliva stimulating agents
5. Flavouring agent
6. Colouring agent
7. Stabilizing and thickening agent

Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient

Generally, 5% w/w to 30% w/w of active pharmaceutical ingredients is incorporated.^[3] In case of multivitamins, up to 10% w/w of dry film weight was loaded.^[4] APIs can be generally milled, micronized or loaded as nanocrystals or particles based on the release profile desired.^[5] For drugs having bitter taste are to be masked before incorporating APIs in the oral strip. In order to enhance the taste different techniques are used but the simplest method includes obscuration technique, which is mixing and co-processing of bitter tasting API with excipient with good and pleasant taste. Specific delivery of the drugs would also be required in allergy, cough, sore throat and local oral manifestations. The main disadvantage of oral film is the dosage form size due to which large amount drug cannot be loaded.

Table 2: Drugs used in oral films.

S.No	DRUG	DOSE	THERAPEUTIC CLASS
1.	Chlorpheniramine maleate	4mg	Anti allergic
2.	Triplolidine hydrochloride	2.5 mg	Anti histaminic
3.	Loperamide	2 mg	Anti diarrhoeal
4.	Famotidine	10 mg	Antacid
5.	Azatidine maleate	1mg	Anti histaminic
6.	Sumatriptan succinate	35-70 mg	Anti migraine
7.	Ketoprofen	12.5 mg	Analgesic
8.	Nicotine	2 mg	Smoking cessation
9.	Pseudoephedrine hydrochloride	30 mg	bronchodilator
10.	Acrivastine	8 mg	Anti histaminic
11.	Dextromethorphan hydrochloride	10-20 mg	Cough suppressant
12.	Loratadine	10 mg	Anti histaminic
13.	Diphenhydramine hydrochloride	25 mg	Anti allergic

Plasticizer

Plasticizer increase mechanical properties like tensile strength and elongation to the film by decreasing the glass transition temperature of the polymer. It also lowers brittleness of the strip as a result improving the flexibility. The Choice of plasticizer depends upon which type of solvent used and its compatibility with the polymer employed. Some of the commonly used plasticizers are derivatives of phthalates like dimethyl, diethyl and dibutyl phthalate, polyethylene glycols with low molecular weight, castor oil, derivatives of citrate like tributyl, triethyl, acetyl citrate, triacetin and glycerol. Plasticizer if not used properly may lead to blooming, film cracking, splitting and peeling of the strip.

Strip forming polymer

Strip forming polymers can be used alone or in combination in order to get the required film properties for the formulation of oral film in order to prevent damage while handling and transportation.^[6] To form the strip, at least 45% w/w of polymers should present because strip-forming polymer is the important constituent of the oral strip.^[7] Generally, 60- 65 of water-soluble polymer is required for preparation of strip with desired properties^[8]. Different polymers used in the formula are given in table 3.

Table 3: Different polymers used in the formula.

POLYMER USED	SOLUBILITY IN WATER	P ^H	MOISTURE (%Loss on drying)	MOLECULAR WEIGHT (kDa)
Hydroxypropyl cellulose	Soluble in water	5-8	1.6	50,000 – 1,250,000
Hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose	Soluble in cold water	5-8	1.6	50,000 – 1,20,000
Sodium carboxymethylcellulose (cmc)	Forms colloidal solution	viscous 6-8	10	90,000 – 700,000
Polyvinyl alcohol	Readily soluble	5-8	5	20,000 – 200,000
Polyethylene oxide	Readily soluble	8-10	<1	variable
kollicoat	>50% in water	6-7		About 45,000

Saliva stimulating agents

In order to increase the rate of production of saliva, saliva-stimulating agents are added. Generally, acids like citric acid, malic acid, lactic acid, ascorbic acid and tartaric acids are stimulants for saliva. These are used in 2-6% w/w of weight of strip. Sweeteners also used as stimulants of saliva (Mahaparale et al, 2012).^[9]

Flavouring agent

The amount of flavouring agent required to mask the taste depends on the type of flavour and its strength. Commonly employed are fruity flavours (cocoa, vanilla, coffee, chocolate, citrus), flavouring oils like (peppermint oil, cinnamon oil, oil of nutmeg). Flavouring agents can also be extracted from oleo resins, synthetic flavour oils and extract derived from parts of the plants eg: flowers, fruits etc.

Colouring agent

Formulation ingredients or drug candidates are present in insoluble or suspension form pigments like titanium dioxide or FD&C (Food, Drug and Cosmetic Act) approved colouring agents are incorporated up to 1% w/w (Kumar Vishwakarma et al.).^[10]

Stabilizing and thickening agent

In order to improve the viscosity and consistency of formulation, stabilizing and thickening agents are incorporated. Cellulose derivatives like Natural gum, xanthan gum, locust bean gum are loaded up to 5% w/w (Kumar Vishwakarma et al.).^[10]

METHOD OF PREPARATION OF ORAL FILMS

Fast dissolving oral films are generally employed using following methods:

- Semisolid casting.
- Rolling.
- Solvent casting.
- Solid dispersion extrusion.
- Hot melt extrusion.

Semisolid casting:

In this method, water soluble solution of film forming polymer is prepared that is added to acid insoluble polymer solution (e.g. cellulose acetate phthalate) which is prepared in ammonium or sodium hydroxide. The ratio of the acid insoluble polymer with respect to film forming polymer should be 1:4. A gel mass is obtained by adding suitable amount of plasticizer. By the means of heat controlled drums, the gel mass is casted into films. The thickness of the film should be 0.015-0.05.

Rolling:

In rolling method, the film is formulated by preparation of pre-mixture i.e., by adding active agent and subsequent formation of film (Rathi et al., 2011).^[11] The pre-mixture batch include polar solvent, film forming polymer and other ingredients except API which are added to the master batch feed tank. Then a predetermined amount of the batch (called master batch) is fed by first metering pump and control valve. Then the desired amount of drug is added into the mixer, and blended for a sufficient time in order to form a homogenized matrix. Certain amount of matrix is fed into the pan through second metering pump. The metering roller determines the thickness of film. The film is finally rolled by the roller and cut into desired shapes.

Solvent casting:

The oral film is prepared by using solvent-extraction method, in which the water-soluble ingredients are dissolved to form a clear and viscous solution. The active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) and other agents are dissolved in small amount of solution and are mixed with the bulk. This mixture is then added into the aqueous solution. The entrapped air is removed and the resulting solution is casted as a film and then dried which is then cut into pieces according to the desired sizes (Sapkal *et al.*, 2011).^[12]

Advantages

- As compared to extrusion method, it has better uniformity of thickness and the film is clearer.
- The wafer is glossier and is free from lines formed due to the die.
- More flexible film is formed with better physical properties.

Disadvantages

- The polymer involved should be soluble in water or any volatile solvent.
- The solution formed should be stable with sufficient solid content and should be viscous.

Solid dispersion extrusion:

In this method, the drug is dissolved in a suitable solvent and then this solution is incorporated in melted PEG below 70 C. The selected solvent or drug should not be miscible with melted PEG and the polymorphic form of drug that is precipitated in solid dispersion may be affected by solvent (Ravindran, 2011).^[13]

Hot melt extrusion:

This method is used to formulate granules, sustained release tablets, transdermal and trans mucosal drug delivery systems. Processing of a film involves shaping a polymer by using the heating process. Initially the hopper is filled with drug carrier and is mixed and then conveyed, mixed and melted by the extruder. Then die shapes the melted mixture into the desired film form. (Repka *et al.* has prepared the chlorpheniramine maleate films by hot melt extrusion method) (Nagaraju *et al.* 2013).^[14]

Advantages:

- Water or aqueous solvent is not required.
- This process does not depend on compressibility properties of API.
- Good bioavailability for poorly soluble drugs.
- Requires less processing time and cost effective.

Disadvantages:

- As there is high temperature, thermal degradation takes place.
- Binders with low melting point, have a risk of melting while handling or storage of the film.

QUALITY CONTROL TESTS FOR ORAL FILMS:**Mechanical Properties:**

Three mechanical properties mainly tensile strength, tear resistance, elastic modulus and percentage elongation are calculated.

Tensile strength

It is the maximum stress applied to a point at which the strip breaks. It is calculated by formula

$$\text{Tensile strength} = \frac{\text{Load at failure} \times 100}{\text{strip thickness} \times \text{strip width}} = \frac{\text{Load at failure} \times 100}{\text{strip thickness} \times \text{strip width}} \times 100$$

Tear resistance

Very low rate of loading 51 mm (2in.)/min is required and is designed in order to measure the force required for tearing. The maximum stress or force (generally found near the onset of tearing) necessary to tear the specimen is known as the tear resistance value in newtons (or pounds- force).

Percentage elongation

It is calculated by using the following formula:

$$\text{Elongation (\%)} = \frac{\text{Increase in length of strip}}{\text{Initial length of strip}} = \frac{\text{Increase in length of strip}}{\text{Initial length of strip}} \times 100$$

Folding endurance

It is calculated by folding the films of uniform thickness at the same place repeatedly until it breaks.

Morphology study

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) at a definite magnification is used to study the morphology of film (Mashru *et al.*, 2005).^[15]

Swelling property

Each film is weighed and placed in a pre-weighed wire mesh. Then the mesh that contains the film is submerged into 15ml of medium (simulated saliva solution) in a plastic container. Increase in the weight of the film was then determined at present time interval until a constant weight was observed.

$$\text{Degree of swelling} = \frac{W_t - W_0}{W_0}$$

Disintegration time

For fast disintegrating films, the disintegrating time limit of 30 sec or less can be used. But there is no official guideline present; this may be used as a qualitative guideline for quality control test. Generally, disintegration time for oral film is 5-30sec (Gavaskar *et al.*, 2010).^[16]

Dissolution test

Dissolution testing can be done by using standard paddle or basket apparatus. The Choice of dissolution medium that is to be used depends upon the sink condition and high dosage of active ingredient (Dixit and Puthli, 2009).^[17] When paddle apparatus is used, dissolution test has problems because of tendency of strip to float on dissolution medium (Nishimura *et al.*, 2009).^[18]

Drug content and content uniformity

Any standard assay methods can be used for the specific API determination of the drug content. Content uniformity is estimated by calculating the API content in individual film. Content uniformity is limited to 85-115%

Organoleptic evaluation

Generally, people accept products that possess features of sweetness and flavours. So in vitro methods like taste sensors, specially designed apparatus and drug release by pharmacopoeial methods are used (Mashru *et al.*, 2005). To differentiate the sweetness level in taste making formulation, experiments are done by using electronic tongue measurements were performed (Anand *et al.*, 2007).^[19]

Stability testing

According to ICH guidelines, oral films have been stored under set conditions of 25°C/60% RH and 40°C/75% over a time period of 12 months. Oral films should be checked for their morphological properties, mass, thickness, reduction of film thickness, tensile properties, water content and dissolution behaviour during storage (Murray *et al.*, 2004).^[20]

Packaging:

Characteristics of Packaging materials:

- They should be packed by FDA.
- They should be tamper resistant.
- Should be non-toxic and should not react with the product.
- Should not affect product colour and taste.

MARKETED PRODUCTS OF ORAL FILMS.

PRODUCT	MANUFACTURER	API	USE
Listerine	Pfizer	Cool mint	Mouth fresheners
Triaminic	Novartis	Dextromethorphan HBr	Cough suppressants
Suppress®	InnoZen®, Inc	Menthol	Mouth fresheners
Chloraseptic	Prestige	Benzocaine menthol	Local anaesthetic
Gas-X	Novartis	Simethicone	Anti flatuating
Theraflu	Novartis	Dextromethorphan HBr	Anti allergic
Setofilm	BioalliancePharma	Ondansetron	Prevention of nausea and vomiting
Zuplenz(R)	MonoSol Rx	Ondansetron	Prevention of nausea and vomiting
Donepezil Rapid film	Labtec	Donepezil	Alzheimer's disease

PREVIOUS REVIEW WORK DONE ON ORAL FILMS:

VENLAFAXINE HYDROCHLORIDE FAST DISSOLVING ORAL FILM

AI- Mogherah et al conducted experiment on venlafaxine hydrochloride to formulate fast dissolving oral films. Venlafaxine hydrochloride is an anti-depressant belonging to the class of serotonin- norepinephrine reuptake inhibitor (SNRI) administered orally. It is structurally known as 1-[2-(dimethyl amino)-1-(4-methoxyphenyl) ethyl] cyclohexanol hydrochloride or (\pm) -1-[α - [(dimethyl – amino) methyl] –p- methoxybenzyl] cyclohexanol hydrochloride. He prepared the films by using solvent casting method. For the formulation, Glycerol was used as plasticizer, saccharine solution was used as sweetening agent, Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) was used as film forming polymer. Full factorial design was used to evaluate the effect of films on disintegration, swelling index. Results showed that the drug content in the films were ranging from 91-100 %, indicating that the drug is stable for 24 hr during its preparation and casting of film.^[21]

NANOSUSPENSION LOADED ORAL FILMS OF GLIMEPIRIDE

Glimepiride belongs to class II of biopharmaceutical class system (BCS) having high permeability and poor aqueous solubility. It is a third generation sulfonyl urea used in the treatment of type 2 diabetes. For the preparation of the film, first nanosuspensions loaded with glimeperide was prepared using high shear homogenization. The film was casted using solvent casting method using hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) E 15, sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), PEG 400. The result obtained was high Cmax and Tmax values and increased bioavailability by converting the nanosuspension into thin oral film.^[22]

SALBUTAMOL SULFATE ORAL FILMS WITH THERMAL INKJET PRINTING

Asma. B.M. Buang et al prepared salbutamol sulfate oral films using thermal inkjet printing. In this method, salbutamol sulfate solutions were prepared and printed on thin clear films (edible potato starch film) using A4 Ryman inkjet printer transparencies, Ryman Ltd. They concluded that thermal inkjet printing method is best suited for printing aqueous solutions. This method is best suited for solutions whose viscosity is between 1.1 and 1.5 mm² s⁻¹.^[23]

PROPRANOLOL HYDROCHLORIDE ORAL THIN FILMS FOR MIGRAINE PROPHYLAXIS

Julie Mariam Joshua et al formulated propranolol hydrochloride oral thin films. It is a beta-adrenergic blocker used in the treatment of migraine prophylaxis. These films were prepared by solvent casting method employing pullulan as polymer. The results concluded that this formulation was more effective in the treatment of migraine.^[24]

CONCLUSION

The success of fast dissolving oral film recently in market is a proof to show the need for effective taste masked, "without water" pharmaceutical formulations. Fast dissolving oral films are a major development of fast dissolving drug delivery systems has shown effective advantages over conventional dosage forms and orally disintegrating tablets. Due to their importance during allergic reactions and high patient compliance, fast dissolving oral films have evolved as an important and convenient dosage.

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